

INNOVATION HUB

CO₂-NEUTRAL GASES & HYDROGEN

NEFI Innovation Hubs are specialised networks led by renowned research institutions. They initiate highly relevant research and innovation projects.

CO₂-neutral Gases & Hydrogen

Target groups: Steel, cement, lime, and chemical industries

Services offered by the NEFI Innovation Hubs

- NEFI Technology Talks:
A range of networking and information events
- Support throughout the entire innovation process: From project idea, application submission, to impact assessment
- Access to state-of-the-art laboratory infrastructure
- Effective dissemination and exploitation of solutions and results

CO₂-neutral gases and hydrogen are becoming increasingly important in industry and offer a promising alternative to fossil natural gas. Particularly green hydrogen, produced through electrolysis using renewable electricity, plays a central role in this context. The required infrastructure can also be used for flexibilisation and sector coupling. For providing high-temperature heat in industrial processes where direct electrification is not possible, CO₂-neutral gases and hydrogen offer an effective solution to replace fossil natural gas.

KEY FOCUS AREAS

Integration of the production, storage, and use of green hydrogen or renewable gases such as biomethane or synthetic methane into existing industrial plants

Techno-economic design of hydrogen infrastructures, development of safety concepts, plant approval, implementation, and operation

Development of comprehensive business cases, transformation scenarios, and project development of infrastructures for renewable gases

CONTACT DETAILS

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HUB CO-LEADS

